

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The mediating role of job satisfaction on the effect of work-family conflict and work stress on turnover intention at PT QIS CERTI Indonesia

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Abstract

In the modern world of work, conflicts between the demands of work and family life as well as excessive psychological and physical stress are the main factors that trigger a decrease in job satisfaction and increased employee intention to leave the company. This phenomenon occurred at PT Qis Certi Indonesia. Based on internal company data in 2023, the employee turnover rate was high. This study aims to analyze the effect of work-family conflict and job stress on turnover intention with job satisfaction as a mediator. The sample was 52 respondents selected through saturated sampling technique. Data collection was done through distributing questionnaires based on a 5-point Likert scale. Data analysis was carried out using the Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) method using SmartPLS software. The results showed that Work Family Conflict and Job Stress have a significant positive effect on Turnover Intention. In addition, Job Satisfaction is proven to mediate the relationship between the two independent variables with Turnover Intention. Active intention to look for another job is the strongest indicator in the Turnover Intention construct with the highest outer loading (0.987).

Keywords: Work-Family Conflict; Job Stress; Job Satisfaction; Turnover Intention

1. Introduction

PT Qis Certi Indonesia is one of the Tourism Business Certification Bodies in Bali that has been accredited by the National Accreditation Committee (KAN). The management of PT Qis Certi Indonesia plays a role as an actor from all levels of planning to the evaluation stage so that it relies heavily on the role of Human Resources. Human Resources in the Company need to carry out effective management in order to have a good impact on the development of the organization, as well as to achieve organizational goals.

Organizational policies that are not in accordance with the expectations and needs of employees will lead to a desire to change jobs (Turnover Intention). During 2023 from January to December, the turnover rate at PT Qis Certi Indonesia was quite high. The number of employees leaving in one year of the 2023 period was 21 employees, with a turnover percentage of 37.8% in 2023.

Several reasons for employees who have a desire that leads to a decision to leave their workplace are generally caused by several factors such as poor management factors, an unsupportive company environment, or dissatisfaction with the performance and results obtained by the employee himself. Factors related to turnover intention are: work-family conflict, job stress and job satisfaction.

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Today's companies with many competitors make them have to really pay attention to the quality of their human resources. So, the factors namely work-family conflict, job stress, job

satisfaction and turnover intention need to be really considered. This is intended to reduce the intention of employees to leave the company, considering that having employees with good performance is not easy to do.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Turnover Intention

Turnover is a term used to describe voluntary resignation or displacement of members of a company or organization. *Intention* is basically an effort made to achieve a goal, with characteristics that can be distinguished from processes related to certain objects. Indicators that are usually used to measure *Turnover Intention* are Intention to Leave, Intention to Search and Alternative Job Opportunities.

2.2. Work-Family Conflict

work-family conflict is a form of conflict between roles caused by conflicting demands of roles at work and family in several ways work-family conflict is a conflict that occurs in individuals due to bearing dual roles, both in work (work) and family (family), where because time and attention are too devoted to one role, so that the demands of other roles cannot be fulfilled optimally. Indicators that are usually used to measure work- family conflict are Time based conflict, Strain based conflict, Behavior based conflict.

2.3. Work Stress

Job stress is identified as a psychological condition of employees characterized by negative responses. Work stress conditions in employees are considered to contribute to employee performance, including a decrease in work productivity. Job stress is often experienced by every employee before starting work, and it can cause behavioral changes in every employee who experiences it. Indicators that are usually used to measure Job Stress are Psychology, Physiology, Behavior

2.4. Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction refers to an effective or emotional response to various aspects of one's job, including employees' perceptions of whether their work is enjoyable or not. It generally reflects the discrepancy between the rewards employees receive and the rewards they believe they deserve. Common indicators used to measure job satisfaction include pay, the nature of the work itself, relationships with coworkers, opportunities for promotion, and supervision

2.5. Research Gap

In the context of turnover intention, where negative attitudes towards work (in the form of low job satisfaction) are a key factor that mediates the influence of work-family conflict and job stress on intention to leave. Overall, this research provides empirical validation of various organizational theories while expanding their application in the context of work culture in Indonesia

2.6. Conceptual Framework

Based on this framework, a schematic conceptual model has been developed to illustrate the role of job satisfaction in mediating the effects of work-family conflict and job stress on turnover intention at PT QIS Certi Indonesia. This conceptual model is presented in the following figure:

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

2.7. Hypothesis of Research

- H1: work-family conflict has a positive effect on turnover intention at PT Qis Certi Indonesia
- H2: job stress has a positive effect on turnover intention at PT Qis Certi Indonesia
- H3: work-family conflict affects job satisfaction at PT Qis Certi Indonesia
- H4: job stress affects job satisfaction at PT Qis Certi Indonesia
- H5: job satisfaction affects turnover intention at PT Qis Certi Indonesia
- H6: job satisfaction mediates the effect of work-family conflict on turnover intention at PT Qis Certi Indonesia
- H7: job satisfaction mediates the effect of job stress on turnover intention at PT Qis Certi Indonesia.

3. Method

This research uses a quantitative descriptive design. The nature of descriptive research has the main objective of making a description of a situation objectively, in order to solve or answer problems that are being faced in the current situation, especially in the fields of Work-Family Conflict, Job Stress, Turnover Intention and Job Satisfaction at PT Qis Certi Indonesia.

In this study, the population consists of all employees who work at PT Qis Certi Indonesia, totaling 52 employees. The sample is part of the population whose characteristics are to be investigated and can represent the entire population so that the number is less than the population. saturated sampling technique is a sampling technique which, if the number is added, will not increase the representation so that it will affect the value of the information obtained or in other words, a sampling technique where all members of the population are used as samples. The reason researchers use this technique is because the population is relatively small, namely 52 respondents.

The process of collecting the data needed in this discussion goes through two stages, namely observation, interviews, questionnaires. To find out the measurement of respondents' answers in this study which used a questionnaire, the authors used the Likert Scale method (Likert's Summated Rattings). Instrument testing uses validity and reliability tests. Validity testing can be done using product moment correlation (Pearson correlation test). The tool to measure reliability is Cronbach Alpha.

Descriptive statistical analysis is statistics used to analyze data by describing or describing the data that has been collected as it is without intending to make conclusions that apply to the public or generalization. In accordance with the hypothesis that has been formulated, in this study inferential statistical data analysis is measured using SmartPLS (Partial Least Square) software starting from model measurement (outer model), model structure (inner model) and hypothesis testing. Outer Model Measurement, Outer model is often called (outer relation or measurement model) which defines how each indicator block relates to its latent variable.

Hypothesis Testing, hypothesis testing is done with the t statistical test (t-test). If this test obtains a p-value of 0.05 ($\alpha = 5\%$), it means that it is not significant. Mediation Testing, testing the mediating variable aims to detect the position of the mediating variable in the research model.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Validity Test

Table 1 Work-family conflict

Item	Correlation Coefficient	Cut Point	Description
X1.1	0.625	0.3	Valid
X1.2	0.462	0.3	Valid
X1.3	0.990	0.3	Valid
X1.4	0.927	0.3	Valid
X1.5	0.990	0.3	Valid
X1.6	0.938	0.3	Valid

Table 1 shows that all questionnaire items have a corrected item value with a correlation coefficient above 0.30, so all questions used to measure work-family conflict variables are declared valid

Table 2 Work Stress

Item	Correlation Coefficient	Cut point	Description
X2.1	0.950	0.3	Valid
X2.2	0.803	0.3	Valid
X2.3	0.855	0.3	Valid
X2.4	0.854	0.3	Valid
X2.5	0.914	0.3	Valid
X2.6	0.873	0.3	Valid

Table 2 shows that all questionnaire items have a corrected item value with a correlation coefficient above 0.30, so that all questions used to measure work stress variables are declared valid.

Table 3 Job Satisfaction

Item	Correlation Coefficient	Cut point	Description
Y1.1	0.702	0.3	Valid
Y1.2	0.985	0.3	Valid
Y1.3	0.985	0.3	Valid
Y1.4	0.810	0.3	Valid
Y1.5	0.985	0.3	Valid
Y1.6	0.731	0.3	Valid
Y1.7	0.950	0.3	Valid
Y1.8	0.985	0.3	Valid
Y1.9	0.985	0.3	Valid

Table 3 shows that all questionnaire items have a corrected item value with a correlation coefficient above 0.30, so that all questions used to measure job satisfaction variables are declared valid.

Table 4 Turnover Intention

Item	Correlation Coefficient	Cut point	Description
Y2.1	0.962	0.3	Valid
Y2.2	0.781	0.3	Valid
Y2.3	0.900	0.3	Valid
Y2.4	0.962	0.3	Valid
Y2.5	0.725	0.3	Valid
Y2.6	0.749	0.3	Valid

Table 4 shows that all questionnaire items have a corrected item value with a correlation coefficient above 0.30, so that all questions used to measure the Turnover Intention variable are declared valid.

4.2. Reliability Test

Table 5 Reliability Test

Variable	Cronbach coefficient	Alpha	Description
<i>Work-family conflict (X1)</i>	0.927		<i>Reliable</i>
Work stress (X2)	0.937		<i>Reliable</i>
Job satisfaction (Y1)	0.967		<i>Reliable</i>
<i>Turnover Intention (Y2)</i>	0.915		<i>Reliable</i>

In table 5, the Cronbach alpha coefficient of each variable shows a value greater than 0.60, so it can be said that all variables that make up the research model are reliable

4.3. Infrential Analysis Result

4.3.1. Outer Model Measurement Results

Table 6 Outer Loading Results

Construct	Original sample (O)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Explanation
X1.1 <- Work-family conflict	0.916	24.494	0.000	Vailid
X1.2 <- Work-family conflict	0.998	547.053	0.000	Vailid
X1.3 <- Work-family conflict	0.911	29.287	0.000	Vailid
X2.1 <- Job Stress	0.947	46.943	0.000	Vailid
X2.2 <- Job Stress	0.995	399.289	0.000	Vailid
X2.3 <- Job Stress	0.918	26.181	0.000	Vailid
Y1.1 <- Job satisfaction	0.968	84.763	0.000	Vailid
Y1.2 <- Job satisfaction	0.964	73.509	0.000	Vailid
Y1.3 <- Job satisfaction	0.955	65.160	0.000	Vailid
Y1.4 <- Job satisfaction	0.957	68.716	0.000	Vailid
Y1.5 <- Job satisfaction	0.968	80.099	0.000	Vailid
Y2.1 <- Turnover Intention	0.968	1052792	0.000	Vailid

Y2.2 <- Turnover Intention	0.987	25.813	0.000	Vailid
Y2.3 <- Turnover Intention	0.931	37.715	0.000	Vailid

In Table 6, it can be seen that the three indicators that measure the work-family conflict variable (X1) have an outer loading value with a range of 0.911 to 0.998 which is greater than 0.50, the T statistic value is above 1, 96 and the p value < 0.05. In reflecting the work stress variable (X 2), because it is proven that all of these indicators have a value outer loading in the range of 0.918 - 0.995 which is greater than 0.50, the T-Statistic value is above 1.96 and the p value < 0.05. In evaluating the job satisfaction variable (Y1), it appears that the five indicators have outer loading values ranging from 0.955 - 0.968 which are above 0.50, the T-Statistic value is far above 1.96 and the p value < 0.05. The test results on the Turnover Intention variable (Y2) show that the three indicators have outer loading values ranging from 0.931 to 0.987 which are greater than 0.50, the T-Statistic value is far above 1.96 and the p value < 0.05.

4.3.2. Discriminant Validity Measurement Results

Table 7 Discriminant Validity Result

Variable	Job Satisfaction	Job Stress	Turnover Intention	Work- family conflict
Job satisfaction	0.962			
Job Stress	-0.666	0.954		
Turnover Intention	-0.848	0.673	0.962	
Work-family conflict	-0.565	0.021	0.544	0.942

Table 7, the results of the *discriminant validity* examination (Table 7) show that the AVE value is greater than 0.50 and the four latent variables studied have a *square root of average variance extracted* (\sqrt{AVE}) value greater than the correlation coefficient between other variables. Thus, the results obtained indicate that it has good *discriminant validity*.

4.3.3. Composite Reliability

Table 8 Composite Reliability

Variable	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_c)
Job satisfaction	0.980	0.984
Job Stress	0.950	0.968
Turnover Intention	0.960	0.974
Work-family conflict	0.936	0.960

Table 8, in accordance with the results of the evaluation of convergent, discriminant validity of each indicator, and composite reliability for the indicator block obtained, it can be concluded that the indicators on each latent variable are valid and reliable measures

4.4. Structural Model Evaluation

Table 9 Structural Evaluation

Structural Model	Dependent Variable	R-Square
1	Job satisfaction (Y1)	0.746
2	Turnover Intention (Y2)	0.780
Calculation: $Q^2 = 1 - [(1 - R(1)^{(2)}) (1 - R(2) (2))]$ $Q^2 = 1 - [(1 - 0,746) (1 - 0,780)] = 0,944$		

Table 9, indicating turnover intention, it is evident that the value of $Q^2 = 0.944$ is close to the value of 1, thus the results of this evaluation provide evidence that the structural model has a good goodness-fit model. this result can be

interpreted that the information contained in the data, 94.4% can be explained by the model while the remaining 5.6% is explained by errors or other variables not contained in the model.

4.5. Direct Hypothesis Test

Table 10 Direct Hypothesis Test

Variable	Path Coefficient	T Statistics	P value	Explanation
Job Satisfaction -> Turnover Intention	-0.427	2.643	0.008	Significant
Job Stress -> Job Satisfaction	-0.654	9.740	0.000	Significant
Job Stress -> Turnover Intention	0.382	3.104	0.002	Significant
Work-family conflict -> Job satisfaction	-0.551	8.378	0.000	Significant
Work-family conflict -> Turnover Intention	0.295	3.007	0.003	Significant

Table 10 states that:

Work-family conflict (X1) is proven to have a positive effect on Turnover Intention (Y2) . This result is indicated by a positive path coefficient of 0.295 with T-statistic = 3.007 (T- statistic > 1.96) and p value = 0.003 (p value < 0.05).

Job stress (X2) is proven to have a positive and significant effect on Turnover Intention (Y2)

. This result is indicated by a positive path coefficient of 0.382 with T-statistic = 3.104 (T- statistic> 1.96) and p value = 0.002 (p value < 0.05).

Work-family conflict (X1) is proven to have a negative and significant effect on job satisfaction (Y1) . This result is indicated by a negative path coefficient of -0.551 with T- statistic = 8.378 (T-statistic > 1.96) and p value = 0.000 (p value < 0.05).

Job stress (X2) is proven to have a negative and significant effect on job satisfaction (Y1) . This result is indicated by a negative path coefficient of -0.654 with a T-statistic = 9.740 (T-statistic> 1.96) with a p value of= 0.000 (p value < 0.05).

Job satisfaction (Y1) is proven to have a negative and significant effect on Turnover Intention (Y2) . This result is indicated by a positive path coefficient of -0.427 with a T- statistic = 2.643 (T-statistic> 1.96) with a p value of = 0.000.

In order to clarify the above explanation, the full model of the SEM-PLS analysis results can be presented in Figure 2 below:

Figure 2 Full Model Analysis Results SEM PLS

4.6. Examination of Mediation Variables

Table 11 Examination Mediation Variables

No	Mediation Variable Job satisfaction (Y1)	Effect Coefficient				
		A	B	C	D	Ket
1	Job Stress -> Job Satisfaction -> <i>Turnover Intention</i>	0.194 (sig)	0.677 (sig)	-0.666 (sig)	-0.719 (sig)	<i>Partially Mediated</i>
2	<i>Work-family conflict</i> -> Job satisfaction -> <i>Turnover Intention</i>	0.096 (sig)	0.545 (sig)	-0.565 (sig)	-0.793 (sig)	<i>Partially Mediated</i>

Table 11, Job satisfaction (Y1) is able to mediate the indirect effect of *work-family conflict* (X1) on *Turnover Intention* (Y2). This result is shown from the mediation test conducted, it appears that the effects of C, D and A have a significant value and the indirect effect path coefficient obtained ≥ 0.10 , which is 0.235.

This result is shown from the mediation test conducted, it appears that the effects of C, D and A have a significant value and the indirect effect path coefficient obtained is ≥ 0.10 , which is 0.279.

Table 12 Examination of Direct, Indirect and Total Effects

No	Variable	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	Total Effect
1	Job satisfaction -> <i>Turnover Intention</i>	-0.427(s)	-	-0.427(s)
2	Job Stress -> Job Satisfaction	-0.654 (s)	-	-0.654(s)
3	Job Stress -> <i>Turnover Intention</i>	0.382(s)	0.279 (s)	0.661(s)
4	<i>Workfamily conflict</i> -> Job satisfaction	-0.551(s)	-	-0.551(s)
5	<i>Workfamily conflict</i> -> <i>Turnover Intention</i>	0.295(s)	0.235 (s)	0.530(s)

Table 12, The path of job stress (X2) to Turnover Intention (Y2) has the largest total effect of 0.661 compared to the path of work family conflict (X2) to Turnover Intention (Y2) which only has a total effect of 0.530. These results suggest that Turnover Intention tends to be determined by job stress, indicating that if job stress increases, it tends to show higher Turnover Intention.

5. Discussion

The results showed that work-family conflict has a positive effect on turnover intention. This means that the higher the level of conflict between work and family experienced by employees, the higher their desire to leave the company. This finding indicates that work-family conflict is one of the important factors influencing the decision of PT Qis Certi Indonesia employees.

The results showed that job stress has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention. This means that the higher the level of work stress experienced by employees of PT Qis Certi Indonesia, the higher the desire of PT Qis Certi Indonesia employees to leave the company. This finding indicates that work stress is one of the important factors influencing the decision of PT Qis Certi Indonesia employees to stay or leave the company.

The results showed that work-family conflict has a negative and significant effect on job satisfaction. Work-family conflict can be considered as one of the high demands of work, so that when employees experience high conflict between work and family, their resources for carrying out work are limited, which in turn reduces their job satisfaction.

The results showed that job stress has a negative and significant effect on job satisfaction. This means that the higher the level of job stress experienced by employees of PT Qis Certi Indonesia, the lower their level of job satisfaction. This

finding indicates that job stress is one of the important factors affecting job satisfaction of PT Qis Certi Indonesia employees.

The results showed that job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention. This means that the higher the level of employee job satisfaction of PT Qis Certi Indonesia employees, the lower the employee's desire to leave the company. This finding indicates that job satisfaction is one of the important factors that influence the decision of PT Qis Certi Indonesia employees to stay or leave the company.

The results showed that work-family conflict has a positive effect on turnover intention, with job satisfaction as a mediating variable. This means that the higher the level of conflict between work and family experienced by employees of PT Qis Certi Indonesia, the lower the level of employee job satisfaction, which ultimately increases the employee's desire to leave the company.

The results showed that job stress has a positive effect on turnover intention, with job satisfaction as a mediating variable. This means that the higher the level of job stress experienced by employees of PT Qis Certi Indonesia, the lower their level of job satisfaction, which in turn can increase employees' desire to leave the company. Job satisfaction acts as a significant partial mediator in the relationship between job stress and turnover intention. High job stress, especially in the form of physiological stresses such as physical fatigue and sleep disturbances, directly reduces the job satisfaction of PT Qis Certi Indonesia employees.

6. Conclusion

In the context of turnover intention, where negative attitudes towards work (in the form of low job satisfaction) are a key factor that mediates the influence of work-family conflict and job stress on intention to leave. When employees feel that the organization fails to meet its obligations in providing a balanced (through high work-family conflict) and healthy (through high job stress) work environment, they will retaliate by reducing their organizational commitment and increasing their intention to leave. Overall, this study provides empirical validation of various organizational theories while expanding their application in the context of work culture in Indonesia. In order to reduce the level of turnover intention, companies need to pay attention to work-family conflict factors, especially the time-based conflict indicator which has the lowest average value compared to other indicators. This finding indicates that time-based conflict between work and family is one of the potential triggers for employees' desire to leave the company. On the work stress factor, companies need to develop mental health programs, for example through stress counseling services and emotional management workshops, to help employees identify and control psychological pressure.

The implementation of these measures is expected to create a more harmonious work environment, thereby increasing employee job satisfaction and ultimately contributing to reducing turnover intention in the Company.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors would like to declare that there are no interested parties to disclose.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants involved in this study. Prior to participation, the purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits of the research were clearly explained to the participants. All participants voluntarily agreed to take part and provided written informed consent. The confidentiality and anonymity of the participants have been strictly maintained throughout the research process.

References

- [1] Ahmad, D. A. F. (2022). The influence of interpersonal conflict, job stress, and work life balance on employee turnover intention. *Journal of Humanities and Education Development*, 4(2). <https://doi.org/10.22161/jhed.4.2>.

- [2] Chan, S.H.J., Ao, C.T.D. (2019), The mediating effects of job satisfaction and organizational commitment on turnover intention, in the relationships between pay satisfaction and work-family conflict of casino employees. *Journal of Quality Assurance in Hospitality and Tourism*, 20(2), 206-229
- [3] Kurniawaty, K., Ramly, M., & Ramlawati. (2019). The effect of work environment, stress, and job satisfaction on employee turnover intention. *Management Science Letters*, 9(6). <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2019.3.001>
- [4] Li, Chen and Gao (2022). Influence of Work-Family Conflict on Turnover Intention of Primary and Secondary School Teachers: Serial Mediating Role of Psychological Contract and Job Satisfaction
- [5] Liu, J., Zhu, B., Wu, J., & Mao, Y. (2019). Job satisfaction, work stress, and turnover intentions among rural health workers: A cross-sectional study in 11 western provinces of China. *BMC Family Practice*, 20(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12875-019-0904-0>
- [6] Novitasari, D., Johan, M., Nadeak, M., Admiral, A., & Asbari, M. (2021). Job stress and turnover intention in the era of industrial revolution 4.0: is there hope in transformational leadership?. *Educative: Journal of Educational Sciences*, 4(1), 443-455. <https://doi.org/10.31004/edukatif.v4i1.1880>
- [7] Wang, Y., Xia, Q., Yue, H., Yu, R., Zhang, W. J., Li, J., ... & Xu, P. (2023). The relationship between work-family conflict and job satisfaction for preschool teachers in rural china: a moderated mediation model. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1236713>
- [8] Xie Y, Tian J, Jiao Y, Liu Y, Yu H and Shi L. (2021) The Impact of Work Stress on Job Satisfaction and Sleep Quality for Couriers in China: The Role of Psychological Capital. *Front. Psychol.* 12:730147. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2021.730147
- [9] Xin Yang, Xiangou Kong, Meixi Qian. (2024). The effect of work-family conflict on employee well-being among physicians: the mediating role of job satisfaction and work engagement.
- [10] Yue Zhang (2019). Work-family conflict and turnover intentions among Chinese nurses, The combined role of job and life satisfaction and perceived supervisor support